

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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IMPLEMENTATION OF A SEPSIS PROTOCOL:
A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Sepsis is the leading cause of death among hospitalized patients but with rapid identification, assessment, and treatment, positive patient outcomes can be achieved. Utilizing the Model of Improvement framework, aim one of this quality improvement project employed a nurse-driven sepsis protocol incorporating the nationally recognized Surviving Sepsis Campaign (SSC) guideline to improve patient outcomes in all units in a community hospital in Southern California. Utilizing the rapid sepsis assessment form, nurses were able to quickly identify signs of sepsis to initiate the nurse-driven protocol to begin life-saving interventions without waiting for physician orders (except for antibiotic selection). SSC bundle elements included lactic acid measurement, blood culture measurement, administration of broad spectrum antibiotic, administration of intravenous fluids, administration of vasopressors, and central venous pressure monitoring; treatments were started as soon as sepsis was validated.

The baseline period of this project took place from November to December 2013. The postimplementation period was November to December 2014. Outcomes evaluated before and after protocol implementation were SSC bundle compliance rate, sepsis patient mortality from all units of hospital, and average hospital length of stay. For aim two of this project, increase in nursing staff knowledge through education were compared before and immediately after sepsis education utilizing a questionnaire. Nurse attitudes about the sepsis epidemic in relationship to sepsis knowledge were also compared. The questionnaire included eight questions assessing attitudes of nurses about the sepsis

epidemic and nine questions assessing nurses' knowledge of recognizing the signs and symptoms of sepsis and had face validity. The questionnaire was administered to nurses who voluntarily participated from all the units before and immediately after a 90-minute sepsis education during the unit staff meetings in fall 2014 with 50% attendance rate.

For aim one, sepsis audit via retrospective chart review revealed that SSC bundle compliance improved with a nurse-driven sepsis protocol. Completion rate of lactic acid went from 64.3% to 88.2% and blood culture completion rates went from 69.2% to 91.2%, vasopressor use from 78.6% to 97.2%, and central venous pressure measurement from 47.6% to 70.6%. Mortality rate and hospital length of stay decreased post implementation although not statistically significantly; lack of significance was most likely due to small sample size.

For aim two, nurses' knowledge after sepsis education improved in recognizing specific signs and symptoms of sepsis.

Despite these encouraging findings and given the fact that only 50% of nurses completed sepsis education, conclusions cannot be drawn about a cause-effect relationship between nurse knowledge and patient outcomes. Future studies are necessary to address the limitations and to determine the most effective way to achieve higher sepsis bundle compliance and to evaluate nurses' awareness of sepsis in relation to patient outcomes.

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BACKGROUND

Sepsis is an overwhelming infection of the body's immune system that occurs when the body is unable to defend against infection and even if treated can lead to multiple organ dysfunction syndrome. In the United States, sepsis is one of the leading causes of death (Hall, Williams, & DeFrances, 2014). Even though it only accounted for approximately 2% of hospitalizations, it made up 17% of hospital deaths (Hall et al., 2014). If left untreated, sepsis can lead to a multitude of complications, including multiple organ dysfunction and even death. Severe sepsis is expensive. The average annual hospital cost is \$14.6 billion (Hall et al., 2014). Due to its severity, a panel of experts comprised of people from 30 international organizations came together to develop guidelines for early diagnosis and treatment of sepsis (Dellinger et al., 2013). This joint effort by the Society of Critical Care Medicine and European Society of Intensive Care was started in 2004 to reduce sepsis mortality by launching the Surviving Sepsis Campaign (SSC). The SSC established a set of clinical practice guidelines for the management of severe sepsis and septic shock based on evidence-based studies (Dellinger et al., 2013). The goal of the SSC is to increase healthcare providers' awareness and improve the outcomes of patients with sepsis, and the evidence has shown the SSC to be effective in decreasing mortality rate (Cardoso, Carneiro, Ribeiro, Teixeira-Pinto, & Costa-Pereira, 2010).

The SSC defines sepsis as the presence of infection with systemic inflammation response syndromes (Dellinger et al., 2013). For a diagnosis of systemic inflammation response syndrome, an individual must meet at least two out of the four following criteria: (a) a temperature greater than 38 degree Celsius or less than 36 degree Celsius,

(b) heart rate greater than 90 beats per minute, (c) respiratory rate greater than 20 breaths per minute or PaCO₂ less than 32 mmHg, and/or (d) white blood cell count greater than 12,000 mm or less than 4,000 mm or greater than 10% bands (Dellinger et al., 2013).

According to the SSC definition, sepsis-induced organ dysfunction is defined as severe sepsis. Septic shock is persistent hypotension associated with severe sepsis that is unresponsive to fluid resuscitative measures (Dellinger et al., 2013). For the purpose of this study, sepsis will encompass sepsis, severe sepsis, and septic shock.

Epidemiology

A review of the sepsis registry revealed the most prevalent organisms found in sepsis were bacterial culture for gram-negative bacteria followed by gram-positive bacteria. Furthermore, fungus is the third most likely causative organism in sepsis (Stearns-Kurosawa, Osuchowski, Valentine, Kurosawa, & Remick, 2011). Although not as prevalent, viruses and parasites can also be causative agents for sepsis (Stearns-Kurosawa et al., 2011). Primary sites of infection include the lungs, the abdomen, and the urinary track. Individuals who develop sepsis are more likely to have other comorbidities, including diabetes, chronic lung disease, congestive heart failure, renal failure, and cancer (Stearns-Kurosawa et al., 2011).

Overall, hospitalized patients with sepsis are two to four times more likely to experience complications and stay in the hospital 75% longer than other patients (Hall et al., 2014). This may occur because patients with sepsis are already more compromised, such as elderly and immunosuppressed patients. Sepsis is associated with poor prognoses, high mortality, frailty, and confounding comorbidities (Hall et al., 2014). Usually, hospitalized patients with sepsis are transferred to short-term acute and long-

term acute care facilities for continuity of care (Hall et al., 2014). Due to the poor prognosis and outcome, it is important to identify sepsis early and treat accordingly to contain comorbidities, mortality, and increased costs of healthcare associated with sepsis.

Pathogenesis

Host inflammatory response is triggered when pathogens enter a sterile environment such as the bloodstream. Mononuclear phagocytes respond to the invasion and produce proinflammatory cytokine and chemokine to facilitate a cascade of reactions and removal of foreign organism. In the case of sepsis, which is an overwhelming infection, high levels of cytokines, bacterial wall lipopolysaccharides, and secondary mediators are released with the following consequences: (a) systemic vasodilation with resultant hypotension and hypoperfusion; (b) diminished myocardial contractility; (c) widespread endothelial injury activation causing leukocyte adhesion and pulmonary alveolar capillary damage; and (d) activation of the coagulation system, often leading to disseminated intravascular coagulation. Prolonged hypoperfusion from an overwhelming infection eventually cause irreversible end organ failure (Stearns-Kurosawa et al., 2011, 2011).

Problem Statement

It is estimated that the cost of sepsis-related hospitalization was \$14.6 billion in the United States in 2008, and this figure is increasing by 11.9% annually (Hall et al., 2014). Patients with sepsis are more critically ill, develop more complications, and have a longer hospital stay. The National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS), a branch of the U.S. Department of Health and Humans Services and Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, reported the number of sepsis hospitalization admissions was 727,000 in

2008. This was a twofold increase from 326,000 reported in 2000 (Hall et al., 2014). Furthermore, the incidence of sepsis increased dramatically with age. According to the NCHS report, the 2008 rate of hospitalization for adults age 65 and older was 122.2 per 10,000 compared to 9.5 per 10,000 for those less than 65 years of age. The incidence is even higher for those over age 85, with a reported rate of 271.2 per 10,000 (Hall et al., 2014).

Due to the debilitating nature of sepsis, early identification and rapid response are critical in interrupting the cascade of events. To improve hospitalization outcomes and reduce mortality associated with sepsis, the SSC recommends the utilization of 3-hour and 6-hour bundles. These are elements of care that have demonstrated success in improving sepsis outcome (Cardoso et al., 2010).

The 3-hour bundle includes measuring serum lactate level, obtaining a blood culture prior to administration of antibiotics, administering broad spectrum antibiotics, and administering 30 ml/kg of a crystalloid solution for hypotension or when serum lactate is greater than or equal to 4 mmol/L. The 6-hour bundle includes administering vasopressors for persistent hypotension (hypotension that does not respond to initial fluid resuscitation) to maintain a mean arterial pressure (MAP) greater than or equal to 65 mmHg and measuring central venous pressure (CVP) and central venous oxygen saturation (Dellinger et al., 2013). Utilization of 3-hour and 6-hour bundles as a group rather than as single interventions has shown to improve sepsis outcomes and reduce mortality (Cardoso et al., 2010). Failure to institute SSC bundle elements in a timely fashion leads to poor patient outcomes, including increased complications, increased length of stay, and increased mortality.

A 210-bed community hospital in Southern California has been fighting a losing battle against sepsis, with the mortality rate high above the U.S. national benchmark of 17% (Hall et al., 2014). The low survival rate is alarming when the evidence clearly demonstrates that early goal-directed therapy reduces sepsis-related morbidity and mortality.

An attempt had been made by this institution to investigate and address the alarming high mortality rate; a preprinted physician sepsis order set incorporating the SSC guidelines was created and had been previously implemented, but the utilization rate was very low. However, this preprinted sepsis order set program was likely unsuccessful because it was based on the old SSC guidelines, was physician driven, and was not promoted to healthcare providers, leading to a low compliance rate. Hence, the mortality rate remained high above the national benchmark. Possible barriers to the success of the sepsis program likely included lack of interdisciplinary collaboration, lack of sepsis knowledge amongst healthcare providers (Bruce, Maiden, Fedulio, & Kim, 2015), and unfamiliarity with the protocol. These barriers have greatly limited the use of existing tools that are available to guide care for this at-risk population. The goal of this quality improvement project was to examine the effectiveness of a nurse-driven sepsis protocol to improve outcomes of hospitalized adults age 18 and older with a diagnosis of sepsis as defined by the SSC. A nurse-driven sepsis protocol relies on nurses to identify signs of sepsis to initiate life-saving interventions. Therefore, it is vital for nurses to possess adequate knowledge and competency. It is hypothesized that nurses' knowledge, behaviors, and attitudes about sepsis directly impact patient outcomes. Hence, the second aim of this project was to seek an answer to the following research question: Do nurses

have knowledge to assess and manage patients with sepsis? Therefore, this current project aimed to improve sepsis outcomes through the implementation of a nurse-driven sepsis protocol and educate nursing staff about sepsis and how to implement the sepsis protocol. This project also aimed to examine nursing attitudes and knowledge relating to sepsis outcome, as failure of early sepsis recognition and unfamiliarity with the protocol are barriers to SSC compliance.

Purpose Statement

The goal of this quality improvement program project was to test the effectiveness of a nurse-driven sepsis protocol to improve outcomes of hospitalized adults with sepsis and to reduce the sepsis mortality rate by 10% from the baseline after implementation of the protocol. This project also aimed to increase nursing staff knowledge through education. Outcome improvement was measured through increased bundle compliance, decreased mortality rate, and decreased hospital length of stay.

Early identification of sepsis and initiation of sepsis bundle reduces sepsis mortality. This DNP project implemented a nurse-driven protocol to expedite the identification and treatment of sepsis. Each patient was assessed for sepsis upon admission, on each shift, and as needed. Upon identification of early signs and symptoms of sepsis, the protocol allowed the nurse to initiate sepsis management interventions without needing to contact the physician. The interventions included nursing actions, laboratory tests, other diagnostic tests, fluid therapy, and other supportive therapies. However, antibiotic selection still necessitated a physician order, considering the possible infection source and other concerns, which are outside the scope of nursing.

SUPPORTING FRAMEWORK

Model for Improvement

The model for improvement was utilized as the framework to guide this quality improvement project with permission (Appendix A). The model for improvement, developed by Associates in Process Improvement, is a change model that aims to generate rapid improvement in processes and outcomes. It is based on W. Edwards Deming's plan-do-study-act (PDSA) cycle and system of profound knowledge (Langley et al., 2009). The model for improvement is comprised of two components, which include three improvement questions and the PDSA cycle (Langley et al., 2009; see Figure 1). The three improvement questions are:

1. What are we trying to accomplish?
2. How will we know that a change is an improvement?
3. What changes can we make that will result in improvement? (Langley et al., 2009, p. 24)

The first improvement question sets measurable aims, including timeline, target population, and affected systems. The second question leads users to quantify measures to demonstrate favorable changes. The last question encourages users to choose variables of previous success (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2014). Overall, the elicited answers from the questions serve as the foundation to guide improvement efforts.

The PDSA cycle, the second component of the model for improvement, is best described as the trial-and-learn step. It is a continuous process of implementation, evaluation, and further implementation. The planning stage begins with the formation of a team of engaged stakeholders. Each team member is assigned a specific responsibility

Figure 1. Model for improvement. Adapted from Langley et al. (2009).

with a regular reporting schedule. The do or action stage is the actual implementation and extraction of data. This then leads to the study stage, which involves data analysis and evaluation of the process. Based on the outcome analysis, maintenance or execution of a new process may be necessary (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2014).

This model for improvement has been widely utilized in healthcare for process and outcome development due to its applicability and ease of use (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2014). Perry, Bell, Shaw, Fitzpatrick, and Sampson (2014) used the PDSA cycle to decrease delay in referral to initial assessment, diagnosis, and treatment time in a memory clinic. After implementation of the PDSA cycle, referral to initial assessment time and referral to diagnosis time decreased from 35.7 weeks to 9.3 weeks and from 15.11 weeks to 14.2 weeks, respectively, indicating that the PDSA cycle was successful in shortening referral to diagnosis and referral to treatment times (Perry et al., 2014).

In another study, Booker, Schluter, Carrillo, and McGrath (2011) noted positive changes in clinical services and delivery systems in school-based health centers after implementing the model for improvement. The positive changes included consistent documentation of student body mass index, physical activity, and nutritional habits; student health questionnaire; early periodic screening diagnosis and treatment components; behavioral health questionnaire; and behavioral health risk assessment.

In a recent study, utilizing the model for improvement to integrate patient safety and clinical pharmacy services resulted in an incredible increase of medication reconciliation compliance of prescription medications, over-the-counter medications, and herbal supplements from 0% to 100% (Robbins, Stillwell, Johnson, Wilson, & Fitzgerald, 2013). This remarkable improvement was accomplished through designation of a single

point of accountability in the pharmacy, centralized medication access through formulary expansion, institution of medication reconciliation guideline, enhanced data access by pharmacy staff, consistent communication of new medications to primary care providers, and implementation of electronic tracking of medications through the patient assistance program (Robbins et al., 2013). Another extraordinary outcome utilizing the PDSA model in the same study resulted in body mass index documentation improvement from 0% to 100% (Robbins et al., 2013).

Finally, this model was employed to examine customer satisfaction in an outpatient clinic (Michael, Schaffer, Egan, Little, & Pritchard, 2013). The study looked at the association between customer satisfaction and length of wait time in the waiting and exam rooms. After implementation of the model, waiting and exam room wait times were shortened by 5.33 minutes and 1.81 minutes, respectively (Michael et al., 2013). The aforementioned studies clearly show that the PDSA cycle is a feasible and successful tool in improving outcomes and sustaining positive changes.

Framework Application

Identify the Purpose of Improvement Efforts

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, patients with sepsis tend to be older, have longer lengths of stay, and develop more complications (Hall et al., 2014). The goal of this quality improvement project was to test the effectiveness of a nurse-driven sepsis protocol to improve outcomes of hospitalized adults age 18 and older with a diagnosis of sepsis as defined by the SSC. Outcomes of interest included mortality rate, hospital length of stay, and protocol compliance. Hospital length of stay was further broken down into length of critical care stay and overall hospital length of stay.

Knowledge deficit was identified by the sepsis committee as one of the barriers to protocol implementation. Knowledge deficit affects sepsis outcome, which results in delayed early goal-directed treatment due to the inability to recognize signs and symptoms. Moreover, knowledge deficit also affects sepsis outcome from unfamiliarity with the protocol to initiate needed interventions. In addition to knowledge deficit, reluctance was identified as a barrier as well. Thus, this study examined nurse knowledge and attitudes in a questionnaire in a pretest and posttest format.

Define Improvement

The current national and state benchmarks for sepsis mortality are 17% (Hall et al., 2014) and 20%, respectively. The target goal for this project was to reduce the sepsis mortality rate by at least 10% to meet the Hospital Association of Southern California's (2015) target. Desired outcomes included decreasing critical care bed days and increasing compliance with the sepsis protocol of assessing the frequency of utilizing SCC 3-hour and 6-hour bundles by nurses.

Aim two of the study compared pretest and posttest results relating to nurse knowledge. A positive survey result, as indicated by an increase in scores, was accomplished through education. Nurses gained knowledge about systemic inflammation response syndrome, stages of sepsis, SSC bundle elements, and facility protocol on sepsis treatment.

Identify Changes That Result in Improvement

Although a sepsis preprinted physician order set already existed, the utilization rate was extremely low. By implementing a nurse-driven protocol instead of a physician-driven process, sepsis bundles were initiated to meet the SCC standards upon

identification of sepsis without getting a physician order. Having a nurse-initiated order protocol removed one of the barriers to battle sepsis, which was physician reluctance to initiate the order set. The implementation had a two-step change process. The first step included early recognition of sepsis by a nurse and implementing the sepsis protocol. This led to the second step of change by using the sepsis order set to initiate the bundle. Since nursing care influences patient outcomes, a thorough assessment of nurse attitudes and knowledge about sepsis diagnosis and treatment were measured utilizing a self-administered questionnaire.

Plan Phase

The stakeholders were identified as hospital administrators, an infection control committee chair who was also an infectious disease physician, infection control practitioner(s), the quality improvement director, the critical care director, the emergency room (ER) director, and critical care charge nurses. These identified members were part of the sepsis committee working to improve sepsis outcome.

A pretest survey was given to nurses to assess their knowledge and attitudes toward sepsis care. Then, based on the findings of this survey, an education program was developed and delivered as a workshop to nurses by the sepsis committee members, including the most current facility sepsis data and the need for a sepsis protocol. Nursing education included how to initiate the protocol when the patient met the criteria. Nursing education also encompassed a lecture and simulation drill based on the existing literature and SCC guidelines in sepsis management. Didactic lecture content included epidemiology, pathophysiology, signs and symptoms, SSC guidelines, facility protocol, and individual roles.

Do Phase

The nurse-driven protocol implementation began after the education and training of staff nurses. During each shift, nurses screened patients for sepsis in all nursing units, including the ER unit, critical care units, medical-surgical units, telemetry units, and other nonspecified units. Criteria for sepsis included infection with at least two systemic inflammation response syndromes. Criteria for severe sepsis included sepsis with induced organ dysfunction. Septic shock was defined as persistent hypotension associated with severe sepsis that was unresponsive to fluid resuscitative measures with a mean arterial blood pressure remaining less than 65 mmHg (Dellinger et al., 2013).

When patients met the criteria in noncritical care areas, a rapid response team (RRT) was called for assessment validation when the unit's primary nurse performed the initial sepsis determination. This triggered the initiation of the sepsis protocol if the patient met sepsis criteria as assessed by a primary nurse and validated by a critical care nurse as part of the RRT. In critical care areas, including the ER, the sepsis protocol was initiated upon nursing assessment by that unit's registered nurses.

Nurse education was delivered through didactic lecture, which encompassed epidemiology, pathophysiology, systemic inflammation response syndrome, stages of sepsis, SSC guidelines, facility protocol, and individual role. High fidelity simulation drills were available as part of the patient safety collaborative from the Hospital Association of Southern California. However, only a limited number of individuals from the critical care areas participated due to the limited number of sessions that were offered by the Hospital Association of Southern California; not all staff could be accommodated.

Study Phase

During the study phase, compliance to the nurse-driven sepsis protocol was examined by auditing SSC bundle completion (Appendix B). Indicators of compliance were measurement of lactic acid level; obtainment of a blood culture prior to antibiotic administration; administration of broad spectrum antibiotics; fluid resuscitation with 30 ml/kg of a crystalloid solution for hypotension or lactic acid level greater than or equal to 36 mg/dL if applicable; administration of vasopressors for hypotension with a MAP less than or equal to 65 mmHg despite fluid resuscitation efforts, if applicable; and measurement of CVP for persistent arterial hypotension. An overall positive increase in bundle element compliance was noted.

In addition, mortality rate and hospital length of stay were reviewed. Retrospective data extracted from the electronic health record were analyzed. Baseline data were gathered before the implementation of the protocol from November 2013 to December 2013. Postimplementation data were collected monthly for 2 consecutive months from November 2014 to December 2014.

Discharge disposition showed a drop in mortality rate in the postimplementation period. It also showed a greater percentage of patients were discharged to home instead of requiring extended healthcare services such as a skilled nursing facility. Even though there was a positive change in patient disposition, length of stay was no different. Critical care bed days and total hospital stay remained unchanged throughout baseline to postimplementation.

Act Phase

Although the study outcomes showed a positive change in the overall bundle compliance rate, there is room for improvement. Education about the sepsis protocol, reinforcement, and close monitoring is necessary to ensure the protocol is followed and bundles are completed. After review of the reasons for failure to comply with the protocol or completion of bundle elements within the timeframe, the sepsis committee will devise a new action plan according to the issues identified for continuous quality improvement.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

The Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL) on EBSCO host, Cochrane, Elsevier Science Direct, Google Scholar, and PubMed National Center for Biotechnology Information were utilized to conduct a literature search through the California State University, Fullerton, library. Keywords and combinations of words used for the search included *nurse-driven protocol*, *sepsis*, *severe sepsis*, *septic shock*, *septicemia*, *bacteremia*, *mortality rate*, *hospital length of stay*, *surviving sepsis campaign*, and *sepsis bundle*. Unless a study was significant to this project, the search was limited to English-language literature published within the last 5 years.

Guideline

Nurse-Driven Protocol

Application of a nurse-driven protocol produces positive outcomes toward achievement of targeted goals. A nurse-driven indwelling urinary catheter removal protocol by Mori (2014) revealed a substantial reduction in the catheter-related urinary tract infection (CAUTI) rate to 0.35% compared to the preimplementation period of 0.77%. The reduction of CAUTI was attributed to (a) avoiding unnecessary urinary catheter insertion and ensuring foley insertion indicators were met (12.5% preimplementation vs. 100% postimplementation), (b) removing the urinary catheter when no longer meeting the indicators (25% preimplementation vs. 12.5% postimplementation), and (c) positioning the urinary catheter to promote downhill flow or urine without a dependent loop (37.5% preimplementation vs. 87.5% postimplementation; Mori, 2014).

Similarly, a nurse-driven process by Bair et al. (2005) demonstrated remarkable improvement in the management of head-injured patients on warfarin, a potent anticoagulant. Through collaboration with trauma services and ER nurses, the protocol instituted key aspects to expedite identification, diagnosis, and treatment for patients who experienced a head injury while on warfarin. The result was a noteworthy improvement of greater than 50% in all aspects of the care process, including mortality rate. After protocol implementation, time to physician evaluation decreased from 31 to 15 minutes, time to computerized tomography scan decreased from 120 to 40 minutes, reversal with fresh frozen plasma decreased from 4 to 3 hours, and mortality decreased from 48% to 10% (Bair et al., 2005).

Screening and Diagnosis

According to the SSC, a critical component of reducing mortality rate and preventing multiple organ dysfunction is through routine screening, which enables early identification, diagnosis, and protocol implementation (Dellinger et al., 2013). To facilitate the identification of causative organisms, appropriate cultures should be obtained prior to antibiotic administration. This is especially important for blood cultures since blood is rapidly sterilized by antibiotics. An aerobic blood culture and an anaerobic blood culture preferably should be obtained from a percutaneous site and a vascular access site if present. This is important in indicating severity and differentiating the infection source. Other cultures, such as cerebrospinal fluid, respiratory secretion, wound, urine, or other bodily fluids, should be considered when suspected as a source of infection. However, cultures may be foregone if the anticipated collection time is greater

than 45 minutes and could lead to a delay in antibiotic administration (Dellinger et al., 2013).

Initial Resuscitation

Early goal-directed therapy (EGDT) should be initiated as soon as sepsis-induced hypotension is recognized. A significant reduction in mortality rate from 38.8% to 25.8% when EGDT was completed was noted in the Nguyen et al. (2007) study. Furthermore, to augment compliance, a protocolized approach has previously shown improvement in meeting SSC measures, including higher compliance with the 6-hour resuscitation bundle and a shorter antibiotic administration time (Giuliano, Lecardo, & Staul, 2011).

Normalizing lactate level is also an important aspect of EGDT because lactate elevation is associated with poorer outcomes (Dellinger et al., 2013), whereas therapy targeting lactate clearance reduces the mortality odds ratio to 0.49 (Nguyen et al., 2007). Mortality rates for patients presenting with hypotension with elevated lactate, hypotension alone, or elevated lactate alone are 46.1%, 36.7%, and 30%, respectively (Dellinger et al., 2013).

Initial fluid resuscitation of 30 ml/kg of crystalloid solution should target CVP between 8-12 mmHg, MAP greater than or equal to 65 mmHg, urine output greater than or equal to 0.5 mL/kg/hr, and superior vena cava oxygen saturation (SvcO₂) greater than 70% or venous oxygen saturation (Svo₂) at 65%. CVP, SvcO₂, and Svo₂ are markers indicating intravascular volumes (Dellinger et al., 2013); therefore, they are utilized to assess perfusion status. Evidence has shown a 15.9% reduction in 28-day mortality rate in septic shock patients who met the target within 6 hours of sepsis onset (Dellinger et al., 2013).

Hemodynamic Control

For initial fluid resuscitation, a crystalloid solution is recommended over a colloid solution since a colloid solution has not demonstrated benefits in clinical trials and it increases the risk of acute kidney injury, with a relative risk of 1.6 (Dellinger et al., 2013). Albumin may be added if a patient's condition requires a large amount of crystalloid solution. For persistent hypotension after initial fluid resuscitation, the addition of vasopressors is necessary to maintain tissue perfusion (Schorr, Zanotti, & Dellinger, 2013).

Norepinephrine is the first choice due to its potent vasoconstrictive effect in reversing hypotension without undesired effects on heart and stroke volume (Dellinger et al., 2013). Epinephrine and vasopressin up to 0.03 units/minute may be added if norepinephrine fails to maintain a MAP greater than or equal to 65 mmHg (Schorr et al., 2013). Alternatively, dopamine may be considered to increase MAP to 65 mmHg and cardiac output. However, dopamine is more prone to cause arrhythmia compared to norepinephrine, with an odds ratio of 1.10 (Dellinger et al., 2013). Therefore, dopamine should be reserved for select patients with low tachyarrhythmia potential. Finally, phenylephrine is not recommended in the treatment of septic shock and is considered a last ditch effort when all other measures fail to maintain a MAP greater than or equal to 65 mmHg (Schorr et al., 2013).

For lactic acidosis, as indicated by serum lactate level greater than or equal to 4 mmol/L, a dobutamine infusion up to 20 mcg/kg/min is indicated to increase oxygen delivery (Schorr et al., 2013). Dobutamine is the first choice of inotrope for patients with suspected low cardiac output despite adequate ventricular filling pressure and MAP

(Dellinger et al., 2013). However, vasopressin therapy is preferred over inotrope if direct cardiac output monitoring is available (Dellinger et al., 2013).

Antimicrobial Therapy

The target goal for antibiotic therapy is to occur within 1 hour of sepsis recognition because the mortality rate increases exponentially with each hour delayed. Mortality reduction at an odds ratio of 1 to 0.38 was noted when antibiotics were received within the targeted timeframe (Nguyen et al., 2007). Broad-spectrum antibiotics should be considered first to cover all likely organisms. Thereafter, antimicrobial regimen should be reassessed daily and should not last more than 5 days if combination therapy was prescribed (Schorr et al., 2013). After the causative organism has been identified and the susceptibility profile is known, an antibiotic regimen must be specific, with the shortest therapy duration to reduce the likelihood of the organism becoming resistant (Dellinger et al., 2013).

Outcomes

Mortality

Early recognition of sepsis and implementation of treatment according to SSC guidelines are critical. Many studies have shown mortality reduction when SSC bundles are completed. Cardoso et al. (2010) cited a significant 28-day mortality reduction to 25% with bundle completion compared to 34% when the bundles were not fully completed. This equated to patients without full bundle completion having a 73% greater chance of death. In a separate study by Li, Xi, Luo, Li, and Li (2013), mortality rate decreased dramatically as the number of elements within the bundle was achieved. They

noted mortality rate dropped to 25% with full bundle compliance, whereas mortality rate soared to greater than 34% when four or fewer elements were completed.

Launched by the SSC steering committee and Institute for Healthcare Improvement, a quality improvement program extended SSC guidelines into bundles of care aimed to improve sepsis patient outcomes (Levy et al., 2010). According to Levy et al. (2010), participating facilities with developed protocols were associated with better patient outcomes and reported a mortality reduction from 37% to 30.8%. Similar results were seen in Na et al.'s (2012) study where the mortality rate was 24.5% when the SSC bundle was completed and 32.7% when incomplete.

Length of Stay

Potential cost savings were projected when following SSC bundle guidelines and hospital length of stay was utilized as an indirect measure of cost savings. Therefore, this present project measured reduction in length of stay as one of the outcomes. Overall, hospital length of stay decreased by 4.8 days from 41 days to 36.2 days after implementing SSC guidelines in the Castellanos-Ortega et al. (2010) study. Furthermore, intensive care unit (ICU) length of stay was reduced as well by 2.6 days from 11 days to 8.4 days (Castellanos-Ortega et al., 2010).

A separate study noted implementation of SSC bundles reduced hospital length of stay by 5 days (Shorr, Micek, Jackson, & Kollef, 2007). In the preprotocol group, 36.7% of patients required hospitalization greater than 2 weeks. This number was reduced to 13.3% after protocol implementation. Furthermore, 20% of patients in the preprotocol group required hospitalization longer than 20 days compared to only 8.3% in the

postprotocol group (Shorr et al., 2007). This translated to \$573,000 in savings according to Shorr et al. (2007).

Complications

In one study, patients who suffered from a greater number of acute organ dysfunctions were less likely to survive and there was an exponential decrease in survival rate with each additional organ dysfunction (Levy et al., 2010). With the failure of four organs, survival rate was less than 50%. The rate was even graver when five or more organs fail, with an estimated survival rate of less than 37% (Levy et al., 2010). Hence, it is imperative that SSC guidelines are followed.

It is established that SSC bundle implementation is associated with greater patient survival and vice versa. Li et al. (2013) reported nonsurvivors were more likely to have acute organ dysfunction and other complications, including hypotension, hyperlactatemia, respiratory dysfunction, renal failure, hyperbilirubinemia, thrombocytopenia, and coagulopathy.

Compliance

By implementing SSC elements in bundles, Levy et al. (2010) reported the overall compliance rate for achieving bundle targets increased from 10.9% to 31.3%. Additionally, compliance of measuring serum lactate increased from 61.0% to 78.7%, obtaining a blood culture prior to administering antibiotics increased from 64.5% to 78.3%, administering broad-spectrum antibiotics increased from 60.4% to 67.9%, administering fluid and vasopressors increased from 59.8% to 77.0%, maintaining CVP greater than 8 mmHg increased from 26.3% to 38%, and maintaining SvcO₂ increased from 13.3% to 24.3% (Levy et al., 2010).

Tromp et al. (2011) reported similar results in achieving statistically significant improvement of SSC elements completion from baseline after implementing sepsis bundling. In another study (Na et al., 2012), instituting bundling of SSC elements demonstrated an increase in full completion of SSC elements from 13.3% to 54.5%. It was further noted that organizations with an established protocol achieved a higher bundle completion at 88.2% compared to 39.5% for organizations without an established protocol. This difference is the primary reason this current project utilized a nurse-driven protocol to ensure full completion of SSC bundle elements.

Derived from evidence-based studies, SSC guidelines are the gold standard for diagnosis and treatment of sepsis. Furthermore, implementation of SSC bundles has demonstrated compliance in completion of measures that improve sepsis outcomes, including mortality rate, hospital length of stay, and complications.

METHODS

To answer the two research questions, this quality improvement project tested “Did utilization of a nurse-driven sepsis protocol improve patient outcomes?” and “Does the nurse’s knowledge, behaviors, and attitudes about sepsis have an impact on patient outcomes?” For sepsis protocol compliance, data were retrieved retrospectively utilizing the facility electronic medical record (EMR) system. For nurse knowledge, data were gathered from the nurse questionnaire. This section outlines the study design, setting, sample, instruments, procedures for data collection, and statistical analysis.

Study Design

This was an evidence-based quality improvement project utilizing a pre and postimplementation design to improve the outcome of patients with sepsis through the incorporation of SSC bundles. A pretest and posttest questionnaire containing 17 questions were used to examine nurses’ knowledge of sepsis and management guidelines. An educational intervention was developed to increase nurses’ knowledge and awareness of sepsis through administration of sepsis identification and management as well as through facilitation of sepsis protocol implementation.

This project incorporated the internationally recognized SSC guidelines and the sepsis order set into a nurse-driven sepsis protocol. This hospital-wide nurse-driven protocol allowed the initiation of a sepsis order set based on nursing assessments and findings. After education about the sepsis protocol to the nursing staff, the protocol was then tested on all hospital units. In noncritical care units, the protocol stipulated that the nurse would notify the RRT whenever a patient met two or more systemic inflammatory response syndrome criteria (fever, hypothermia, tachycardia, or tachypnea) in association

with suspected infection and signs of hypoperfusion. This is consistent with the facility policy to initiate the RRT in noncritical care areas whenever there is a change or concern of the patient's condition that warrants quick assessment, early intervention, and stabilization to prevent clinical deterioration.

The core members of the RRT were a critical care nurse, a nursing house supervisor, a unit charge nurse, the primary nurse of the patient, a respiratory therapist, a laboratory technician, and an electrocardiogram technician. A critical care nurse reviewed patient information with the primary nurse of the patient and then performed an intensive assessment to determine the status of the patient. If the RRT identified probable sepsis, a sepsis protocol was activated. Patients determined by the RRT to have septic shock or needing vasopressors to maintain a MAP greater than or equal to 65 mmHg or needing additional supportive therapy outside the capabilities of noncritical areas were transferred to critical care for continuity of care.

For critical care areas, including ER and critical care units, the sepsis protocol was activated based on nurse assessments of systemic inflammation response syndromes, sepsis, severe sepsis, and septic shock. Laboratory tests, including lactic acid level, anaerobic and aerobic blood cultures, and other lab tests, were drawn. Fluid resuscitation and vasopressors were initiated if indicated to keep MAP greater than or equal to 65 mmHg (see Figure 2). The study protocol involved (a) serum lactic acid level measurement, (b) blood culture collection before antibiotic initiation, (c) broad-spectrum antibiotic administration, and (d) a weight-based intravenous (IV) fluid bolus infusion (30 mL/kg of crystalloid solution over a period of 30 minutes; Figure 2).

Figure 2. A nurse-driven sepsis protocol.

Setting

The study setting was noncritical care units, including a telemetry unit, a medical-surgical unit, and a rehab unit, and critical care units, including ICU units and an ER unit, at a 200-bed community medical center located in Southern California. This study examined differences between septic patient outcomes before and after implementation of a nurse-initiated sepsis protocol. This study was also interested in finding whether nurse attitudes and knowledge have an effect on sepsis outcome by linking nurses' knowledge of sepsis to patient outcomes.

Data Collection

This study consisted of two arms, implementing a nurse-driven sepsis protocol and developing and implementing a sepsis management education program. Data collection for first study arm occurred by retrospective chart review before and after protocol implementation. Data were retrieved utilizing the facility EMR system. An audit tool was programmed by the investigator into the EMR to generate a list of patients with sepsis (995.91), severe sepsis (995.92), and septic shock (785.52) by the International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Revision (ICD-9) were included in the sample. An additional inclusion criterion included those age 18 and older. Exclusion criteria included patients under the age of 18 years, patients with a partial or complete do-not-resuscitate order, and/or patient refusal of any part of the study measurements.

Baseline data were collected based on patient discharge dates from November 1, 2013, to December 31, 2013. Postimplementation data were collected based on patient discharge dates from November 1, 2014, to December 31, 2014. The investigator

evaluated protocol compliance by measuring performance as described in the Study Measures section.

The second aim of this study assessed whether nurses' attitudes about the sepsis epidemic and knowledge of sepsis management have an effect on sepsis outcome. To answer this question, the investigator utilized a questionnaire to assess the attitudes and knowledge of nurses before and after sepsis education was provided.

Study Measures

Demographic Characteristics

Demographic characteristics were assessed using a demographic data sheet developed by the investigator. Patient demographic characteristics included age, gender, ethnicity, and location upon sepsis diagnosis. Staff demographic characteristics were also assessed, including age, gender, employment status (full time, part time, or per diem), education level, specialty area, years in the current hospital, and years of experience.

Assessment

To enable quick identification, the investigator developed a rapid sepsis assessment form according to SSC criteria for nurses. The form referred to the nurse-driven protocol to help guide nurses in the management of sepsis patients (Figure 2).

Protocol Compliance

To measure nurses' compliance with the sepsis protocol within 3 hours of initiating the sepsis protocol, the following measures were required to be met for patients with sepsis, severe sepsis, and septic shock: (a) serum lactic acid level (serum lactate level was substituted for serum lactic acid level due to facility operation limitations); (b)

blood culture prior to the administration of antibiotics, (c) administration of broad-spectrum antibiotics; and (d) administration of 30 ml/kg crystalloid, if applicable, for hypotension as evident by $MAP \leq 65$ mgHg or serum lactic acid ≥ 36 mg/dL (Dellinger et al., 2013).

To measure nurses' compliance with the sepsis protocol within 6 hours, the following measures were required to be met for patients with septic shock: (a) application of vasopressors, if applicable, for hypotension that did not respond to initial fluid resuscitation needed to keep $MAP \geq 65$ mmHg and (b) measurement of CVP, if applicable. For the purpose of this study, measurement of CVP was only indicated when vasopressor therapy was required (Dellinger et al., 2013).

Although monitoring of central venous oxygen saturation is part of the SSC 6-hour bundle, it was excluded as part of measuring compliance for this study because the facility in this study did not have an established process or the capability to perform the test.

Instruments

Sepsis audit tool. A standardized data collection tool with face validity was developed by the investigator and used to extract patient information from the EMR system, including admission date; patient age, sex, and ethnicity; ICD diagnosis; volume of fluid infused; blood culture and serum lactate level results; antibiotic administration time; location of sepsis identification; hospital length of stay; in-hospital mortality; bundle compliance; and discharge disposition (Appendix B).

Nurse survey. A questionnaire was used to assess nurses' knowledge of sepsis and management guidelines before and after the intervention (Appendix C). It was

adapted from the Robson, Beavis, and Spittle (2007); Stamataki et al. (2013); and Ziglam, Morales, Webb, and Nathwani (2006) studies. It was designed by experts from the Hellenic Sepsis Study Group and has content validity; however, reliability data were not reported in the literature (Stamataki, 2013). Furthermore, the questionnaire was reviewed by the facility sepsis committee members and deemed to have face validity.

The questionnaire included eight questions assessing attitudes of nurses about the sepsis epidemic and nine questions assessing nurses' knowledge of recognizing the signs and symptoms of sepsis and had face validity. In addition, a participant demographics inquiry was incorporated into the questionnaire.

Procedure

The California State University, Los Angeles, Institutional Review Board and the medical center administration approved the study protocol. This project adhered to the regulations of the Health Insurance Portability and Protection Act (HIPPA) to protect the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants. To safeguard patient confidentiality and privacy, the facility and the investigator established a limited data use agreement. A limited data set containing limited patient identifiable information, as defined and allowed by HIPPA, was utilized. All other patient identifiers were removed, including the following: names, street addresses (other than town, city, state, and zip code), telephone numbers, fax numbers and mail addresses, social security numbers, medical record numbers, health plan beneficiary numbers, account numbers, certificate license numbers, vehicle identifiers and serial numbers (including license plates), device identifiers and serial numbers, uniform resource identifier (URL), Internet protocol (IP)

address numbers, biometric identifiers (including finger and voice prints), and full face photos (or comparable images).

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS 22.0 for Windows. The demographic characteristics of the participants were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, or chi-squares. Chi-squares and *t* tests were used to measure changes in knowledge, attitudes, behaviors, compliance, and outcomes. A statistical significance of .05 was employed. Patient outcomes were compared between pre and postprotocol implementation periods.

RESULTS

Sepsis Outcome

Sample Characteristics

This analysis included 76 sepsis patients, with 42 in the baseline group and 34 in the postimplementation group. Nine cases were excluded from the baseline sample and 13 cases were excluded from the postimplementation sample due to meeting the exclusion criteria. The mean patient age was 74 years ($SD = 16$) at baseline and 76 years ($SD = 12$) at postimplementation. Furthermore, males and females were equally distributed. No statistically significant differences were found between the pre and postimplementation groups for any patient characteristics. Patient demographic and clinical characteristics ($N = 76$) are shown in Table 1.

More than two thirds of the patients had an ICD diagnosis of septic shock at pre and postprotocol implementation (71.4% vs. 79.4%, respectively). Before protocol implementation, most patients presented with sepsis in the ER (78.6%; $n = 33$). Similarly, at postimplementation, the ER remained the location with the highest sepsis identification (91.2%; $n = 31$), followed by critical care (5.9%; $n = 2$). However, no statistically significant differences were found between the pre and postprotocol groups for any patient characteristics.

Discharge Disposition

It is of clinical significance, although not statistically, mortality rate dropped from 28.6% ($n = 12$) at baseline to 20.6% ($n = 7$) after implementation. Patients requiring transfer to a higher level of care or to a tertiary center decreased from 9.5% ($n = 4$) to 2.2% ($n = 1$). The discharge rate to home with or without home health increased from

Table 1

Patient Demographic Characteristics

	Before protocol (<i>n</i> = 42) <i>n</i> (%)	After protocol (<i>n</i> = 34) <i>n</i> (%)	Total (<i>N</i> = 76) <i>n</i> (%)	<i>X</i> ²	<i>p</i>
ICD 9				2.85	.82
Sepsis	3 (7.1%)	4 (11.8%)	7 (9.1%)		
Severe sepsis	9 (21.4%)	3 (8.8%)	12 (15.6%)		
Septic shock	30 (71.4%)	27 (79.4%)	58 (75.3%)		
Gender				2.27	.31
Male	21 (50.0%)	21 (61.8%)	42 (54.5%)		
Female	21 (50.0%)	13 (38.2%)	35 (45.5%)		
Ethnicity				4.75	.05
White	15 (35.7%)	6 (17.6%)	21 (27.3%)		
Black	3 (7.1%)	1 (2.9%)	4 (5.2%)		
Asian	24 (57.1%)	27 (79.4%)	52 (67.5%)		
Level of Care				10.13	.86
Critical care	6 (14.3%)	2 (5.9%)	9 (11.7%)		
ER	33 (78.6%)	31 (91.2%)	64 (83.1%)		
Telemetry	2 (4.8%)	1 (2.9%)	3 (3.9%)		
Med-surg	1 (2.4%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.3%)		

12.6 % (*n* = 7) to 30.4% (*n* = 10) and to skilled nursing facilities decreased from 33.3% (*n* = 14) to 29.4% (*n* = 10). However, discharge to long-term acute care increased slightly from 9.5% (*n* = 4) to 11.8% (*n* = 4).

Length of Stay

There was not a statistically significant difference between baseline and postimplementation length of stay in critical care units, noncritical care areas, and total length of stay utilizing a chi-square of independence. Baseline critical care, noncritical care, and total length of stay were 3.97 (*SD* = 4.03), 5.98 (*SD* = 7.78), and 9.95 (*SD* =

8.43), respectively. Postimplementation in the same areas were 4.94 ($SD = 6.13$), 7.41 ($SD = 6.76$), and 12.12 ($SD = 9.32$), respectively.

Pre and Postprotocol Comparisons

SSC bundle compliance and patient outcome comparisons between the two groups are shown in Table 2. A chi-square of independence revealed that, among this sample of 76 cases, there was a statistically significant association between baseline and postimplementation bundle compliance ($\chi^2_{(12)} = 28.17, p < .05$). Prior to implementation, 9.8% ($n = 4$) failed to complete any SSC bundle elements within the timeframe. Conversely, after implementation, at least one of the SSC bundle elements was completed. Moreover, 88.2% ($n = 30$) completed four or more bundle elements postimplementation compared to only 68.3% ($n = 28$) at baseline. For five or more bundle completions, there was an improvement from 48.8% ($n = 20$) to 79.4% ($n = 27$). Finally, there was an improvement from 24.4% ($n = 10$) to 55.9% ($n = 19$) for the completion of all six bundles.

A chi-square test of independence revealed that there was a statistically significant association between baseline and postimplementation blood culture compliance ($\chi^2_{(2)} = 8.924, p < .05$; Figure 3). An independent samples t test revealed, among this sample of 76 cases, a statistically significant difference in blood culture compliance between baseline ($M = 1.31$) and postimplementation ($M = 1.09$; $t_{(69)} = 2.53, p = .05$; see Table 1). An independent samples t test also revealed a statistically significant difference in lactic acid compliance between baseline ($M = 0.64$) and postimplementation ($M = 0.88$; $t_{(72)} = -2.56, p = .01$; Figure 4).

Table 2

Bivariate Pre Versus Postprotocol Comparisons (N = 76)

	Before protocol (n = 42)	After protocol (n = 34)	p value for pre versus postprotocol comparison
Serum lactic acid measurement	27 (64.3%)	30 (88.2%)	*.01
Blood cultures before antibiotics	29 (69.0%)	31 (91.2%)	*.01
Broad-spectrum antibiotic administration	27 (65.9%)	27 (79.4%)	.19
Fluid administration: ≥ 30 mL/kg if patient had hypotension or lactic acid ≥ 36 mg/dL	33 (78.6%)	31 (91.2%)	.12
Vasopressor for persistent hypotension	33 (78.6%)	33 (97.2%)	*.01
CVP	20 (47.6%)	24 (70.6%)	*.04
Length of hospital stay, mean, SD, median (range)	9.95 \pm 8.43, 7 (34)	12.12 \pm 9.32, 9.5 (31)	
In-hospital mortality	12 (28.6%)	7 (20.6%)	.43

Note. Values are expressed as number (percent) unless otherwise indicated. We used the *t* test for continuous variables and the χ^2 test for categorical variables.

p* < .05. *p* < .01.

Figure 3. Blood culture completion.

Figure 4. Lactic acid completion.

Moreover, an independent samples *t* test also revealed a statistically significant difference in application of vasopressor between baseline ($M = 0.79$) and postimplementation ($M = 0.97$; $t_{(57)} = -2.62$, $p = .01$; Figure 5). An independent samples *t* test also showed a statistically significant difference in CVP compliance between baseline ($M = 2.43$) and postimplementation ($M = 2.71$; $t_{(74)} = -2.39$, $p = .05$; Figure 6). A chi-square test also revealed an association between total bundle compliance and location of sepsis identification ($\chi^2_{(18)} = 56.10$, $p < .001$). Bundle completion was highest with sepsis diagnosed in the ER at 87.3% with four or more bundles. Conversely, SSC bundle completion was only 33.3% and 22.2% when diagnosed in telemetry and critical care, respectively.

Moreover, an independent samples *t* test also revealed a statistically significant difference regarding total bundle completion when identified in critical care ($M = 2.44$) and ER ($M = 4.98$; $t_{(70)} = -5.53$, $p < .001$). There was also a statistically significant difference when sepsis was diagnosed in the ER ($M = 4.98$) and telemetry ($M = 2.33$; $t_{(64)} = 3.43$, $p < .001$).

Nurses' Knowledge of Sepsis

Sample Characteristics

Demographic characteristics assessed included age, gender, marital status, education level, employment status (full time, part time, or less than part time), title (registered nurse or licensed vocational nurse), and area of work.

A total of 182 nurse questionnaires were completed and included in the analysis in the second arm of the study; 50% ($n = 91$) were pretests and 50% ($n = 91$) were

Figure 5. Vasopressor application.

Figure 6. CVP measurement.

posttests. There were no statistically significant differences between the pre and posttest groups for any demographic characteristic, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Nurse Survey Demographic Characteristics

	Pretest (<i>n</i> = 91) <i>n</i> (%)	Posttest (<i>n</i> = 91) <i>n</i> (%)	Total (<i>n</i> = 182) <i>n</i> (%)
Gender			
Female	76 (84.4%)	67 (80.7%)	143 (82.7%)
Male	14 (15.6%)	16 (19.3%)	30 (17.3%)
Marital Status			
Single	26 (28.6%)	26 (31.3%)	52 (29.9%)
Married	57 (62.6%)	52 (62.7%)	109 (62.6%)
Divorced/Separated	3 (3.3%)	2 (2.4%)	5 (2.9%)
Widowed	5 (5.5%)	3 (3.6%)	8 (2.6%)
Education Level			
Diploma	14 (15.4%)	15 (18.1%)	29 (16.7%)
Associate	50 (54.9%)	48 (57.8%)	98 (56.3%)
Bachelor	20 (22.0%)	13 (15.7%)	33 (19.0%)
Graduate or higher	7 (7.7%)	6 (7.2%)	13 (7.5%)
Employment Status			
Full time	88 (96.7%)	78 (94.0%)	166 (95.4%)
Part time	2 (2.2%)	4 (4.8%)	6 (3.4%)
< Part time	1 (1.1%)	1 (1.2%)	2 (1.1%)
Title			
RN	80 (90.9%)	75 (91.5%)	155 (92.1%)
LVN	8 (9.1%)	7 (8.5%)	15 (8.8%)
Area Worked			
Critical Care	11 (12.1%)	9 (11.0%)	20 (11.6%)
ER	35 (38.5%)	35 (43.4%)	71 (40.8%)
Telemetry	20 (30.8%)	23 (27.7%)	51 (29.3%)
Medical/Surgical	13 (14.4%)	10 (11.0%)	23 (12.6%)
Other			

Nurse Attitudes and Knowledge About Recognizing Sepsis

An independent samples *t* test revealed, among this sample of nurses, a statistically significant difference in nurse attitudes scores toward the sepsis epidemic between the pretest ($M = 8.10$) and posttest ($M = 7.82$; $t_{(178)} = -3.51$, $p = .01$).

A chi-square test of independence revealed, among the sample of 182 survey answers, a statistically significant association between pretest and posttest knowledge of decrease in MAP value as a sign of suspected sepsis ($\chi^2_{(1)} = 17.230$, $p < .001$). A chi-square test of independence also revealed, among the sample of 182 survey answers, a statistically significant difference between pretest and posttest knowledge of increase in blood glucose value as a sign of suspected sepsis ($\chi^2_{(1)} = 9.610$, $p < .005$). A chi-square test of independence further revealed, among the sample of 182 survey answers, a statistically significant association between pretest and posttest knowledge of increase in iron and serum ferritin value as a sign of suspected sepsis ($\chi^2_{(1)} = 18.016$, $p < .001$).

Examining the standardized residuals revealed that more nurses than expected answered incorrectly during the pretest and fewer than expected answered incorrectly during the posttest on the question regarding decrease in MAP as a suspected sign of sepsis. Further examination of the standardized residuals also revealed fewer nurses than expected answered correctly during the pretest and more than expected answered correctly during the posttest to the question regarding increase in iron and serum ferritin value as a sign of suspected sepsis.

Although there was a statistically significant correlation between nurse education level and nurse attitudes toward daily sepsis assessment, the correlation was less than modest. Similarly, there was a statistically significant yet less than modest association

between years of experience and knowledge of urine output and serum iron as signs of sepsis. Likewise, there was a less than modest association between nurses working in the ER and knowledge regarding tachypnea, white blood cell count, MAP, blood glucose, and oxygen as signs and symptoms of sepsis.

DISCUSSION

Results

A nurse-driven sepsis protocol was more effective than a physician-driven protocol in improving sepsis outcome in this present study. SSC bundle compliance increased from baseline, especially lactic acid, blood culture, vasopressor application, and CVP measurement. This is consistent with other studies that found an improvement in SSC bundle indicators and overall compliance rate, which increased after application of the sepsis guideline protocol such as in Wang, Xiong, Schorr, and Dellinger (2013) and Bruce et al. (2015). In Wang et al., SSC bundle adherence improved dramatically in the emergency department in China. Similarly, Bruce et al. (2015) found 3-hour SSC bundle compliance—serum lactate measurement and obtaining blood cultures before antibiotic administration—was nearly perfect in the postprotocol group.

Overall, when sepsis was identified in the ER, bundle completion rate was higher compared to when sepsis was identified in other departments. It may be that previous sepsis implementation, which was a physician-driven process, was implemented in the ER. Thus, nurses and physicians were more familiar with sepsis due to more education and exposure. Moreover, ER physicians are contracted agents subject to performance review and are expected to align with facility-directed initiatives. In contrast, departments outside of the ER may have had less exposure and less experience in handling sepsis patients.

Despite SSC bundle compliance improvement, mortality and hospital length of stay did not differ. Nonetheless, the mortality rate decreased from 28.6% at preimplementation to 20.6% at postimplementation. The target goal of 10% mortality

reduction was achieved. Although this was not statistically significant, it was of great clinical significance and validation of SSC guidelines.

Although it was of clinical significance that the mortality rate decreased to 20.6% from 28.6% after implementation, statistically it was not significant. This is consistent with the findings by Bruce et al. (2015) and Yealy et al. (2014) that protocol-based care for sepsis yielded no different outcome in the death rate even with high protocol adherence. In addition, the protocol-based care group even experienced a higher incidence of the need for renal replacement therapy. With that said, reports of adverse events were rare and were no different across groups (Yealy et al., 2014). Yealy et al. also indicated there were no significant differences in length of stay in critical care and length of stay in the hospital. Nonetheless, this study's finding was in contrary to the report. This may be due to the small sample size of the study, which did not allow for a detection of differences. A future study with a larger sample is needed to validate the findings.

In this study, a nurse-driven process led to favorable discharge disposition. Once again, it is of clinical significance that patients were more likely to return to their baseline functional status and go home without additional assistance or with limited assistance as evident by an increase in number of discharges to home with or without home health (30.4% after implementation); however, the difference was not statistically significant. The Yealy et al. (2014) study also generated the same result where incidence of discharge disposition did not significantly differ. Overall, patients were less likely to require additional assistance or be transferred to a tertiary care center due to deterioration of conditions. This was mainly due to a standardized assessment that enabled nurses to

perform a quick assessment for early sepsis identification and, subsequently, initiate interventions and elements meeting SSC criteria.

According to Barochia et al. (2010), studies have cited that utilization of educational programs and aids such as sepsis carts, tool kits, nursing flow sheets, and dedicated lines of communication with infection experts improve the process leading to desired patient outcomes. In this study, nurses who participated in the sepsis education program had a higher knowledge of sepsis signs and symptoms relating to MAP, blood glucose value, and iron and serum ferritin. However, a cause and effect conclusion still cannot be drawn that education influenced nurses' behaviors using the nurse-driven sepsis protocol.

Limitations

The nursing survey questionnaire was adapted from the Stamataki et al. (2013) study, which revised the questionnaires that were used in the Ziglam et al. (2006) and Robson et al. (2007) studies to assess sepsis-related knowledge. This questionnaire was designed by experts from the Hellenic Sepsis Study Group and has content validity (Stamataki et al., 2013). Unfortunately, no reliability data were reported in the literature. This challenged the reliability of the questionnaire. Nonetheless, the questionnaire was reviewed by the facility sepsis committee members and deemed to have face validity.

Another limitation of the study was that the design of the questionnaire was not exhaustive for the assessment of sepsis patients. A questionnaire containing additional questions regarding the assessment of systemic inflammation response syndrome and sepsis signs and symptoms should be incorporated in future studies.

The small sample size of sepsis cases may lessen generalizability and contribute to a type II error. This was mainly due to time constraints between the delayed IRB approval time and project completion. Future investigations should allow for more time prior to protocol implementation to allow for more participants.

Implications

SSC bundle compliance is associated with positive patient outcomes, but increased SSC bundle compliance did not result in a change in mortality and length of stay in this study. Given the relatively small sample size in this study, baseline and postimplementation differences may not have been detected. Furthermore, future studies including a larger sample size are necessary to find differences.

This present study showed nurse attitudes and knowledge scores increased after sepsis education occurred. Although a cause-effect relationship could not be established, a link between nursing care and sepsis outcome cannot be ruled out. Historically, very limited sepsis education has been taught in nursing programs. Lack of understanding can lead to missed opportunities for early goal-directed sepsis therapy, resulting in undesirable outcomes. An implication is that nursing schools need to incorporate in-depth sepsis education into the curriculum, emphasizing recognition and treatment of sepsis.

Conclusions

Nurses play a vital role in early recognition and treatment of septic patients. This study showed that a nurse-driven sepsis protocol improved SSC guideline-recommended bundle compliance by eliminating the delay from waiting for a physician order. Rapid identification and timely treatment of septic patients with severe sepsis or septic shock can reduce hospital length of stay and mortality rates. In this study, a nurse-initiated

sepsis protocol significantly improved bundle compliance in obtaining lactic acid, blood culture, application of vasopressor, and CVP monitoring. However, although clinically significant, protocol implementation produced no statistically significant changes in hospital length of stay and mortality rate.

The results of this present study also showed that education increased nurse attitudes and knowledge scores. However, it cannot be determined that nurse knowledge altered nurses' behaviors and care of the patients. Future research is necessary to determine the most effective way to achieve higher sepsis bundle compliance and to evaluate nurses' awareness of sepsis in relation to patient outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Bair, H., Ivascu, F., Janczyk, R., Nittis, T., Bendick, P., & Howells, G. (2005). Sharing our best nurse driven protocol for head injured patients on warfarin. *Journal of Trauma Nursing, 12*, 120-128.
- Barochia, A. V., Cui, X., Vitberg, D., Suffredini, F., O'Grady, N. P., Banks, S. M., . . . Eichacker, P. Q. (2010). Bundled care for septic shock: An analysis of clinical trials. *Critical Care Medicine, 38*, 668-678. doi:10.1097/CCM/ob013e3181cb0ddf
- Booker, J. M., Schluter, J. A., Carrillo, K., & McGrath, J. (2011). Quality improvement initiatives in school-based health centers across New Mexico. *Journal of School Health, 81*, 42-48. doi:10.1111/j.1746-1561.2010.00556.x
- Bruce, H. R., Maiden, J., Fedulio, P. F., & Kim, S. C. (2015). Impact of nurse-initiated ED sepsis protocol on compliance with sepsis bundles, time to initiate antibiotics administration, and in-hospital mortality. *Journal of Emergency Nursing, 41*, 130-137. doi:10.1016./jen.2014.12.007
- Cardoso, T., Carneiro, A. H., Ribeiro, O., Teixeira-Pinto, A., & Costa-Pereira, A. (2010). Reducing mortality in severe sepsis with the implementation of a core 6-hour bundle: Results from the Portuguese community-acquired sepsis study (SACiUCI study). *Critical Care, 14*, 1-11. Retrieved from <http://ccforum.com/content/14/3/R83>
- Castellanos-Ortega, A., Suberviola, B., Garcia-Astudillo, L. A., Holanda, M. S., Ortiz, F., & Delgado-Rodriguez, M. (2010). Impact of the Surviving Sepsis Campaign protocols on hospital length of stay and mortality in septic shock patients: Results of a three-year follow-up quasiexperimental study. *Critical Care Medicine, 38*, 1036-1043. doi:10.1097/CCM.0b0b13e3181d455b6
- Dellinger, R. P., Levy, M. M., Rhodes, A., Annane, D., Gerlach, H., Opal, S., . . . Moreno, J. (2013). Surviving Sepsis Campaign: International guidelines for management of sepsis and septic shock: 2012. *Journal of Critical Care Medicine, 41*, 580-637. doi:10.1097/CCM.0b013e31827e83af
- Giuliano, K. K., Lecardo, M., & Staul, L. (2011). Impact of protocol watch on compliance with the Surviving Sepsis Campaign. *American Journal of Critical Care, 20*, 313-322.
- Hall, M. J., Williams, S. N., & DeFrances, C. J. (2014). Trends in inpatient hospital patient death: National hospital discharge survey 2000-2010. *NCHS Data Brief, 118*. Retrieved from <http://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/databriefs/db118.pdf>

- Hospital Association of Southern California. (2015). *Southern California Patient Safety First Collaborative*. Retrieved from <http://www.hasc.org/southern-california-patient-safety-first-collaborative>
- Institute for Healthcare Improvement. (2014). *The science of improvement*. Retrieved from <http://www.ihl.org/resources/Pages/HowtoImprove/ScienceofImprovementHowtoImprove.aspx>
- Langley, G. L., Moen, K. M., Noland, K. M., Noland, T. W., Norman, C. L., & Provost, L. P. (2009). *The improvement guide: A practical approach to enhancing organizational performance* (2nd ed.). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Levy, M. M., Dellinger, R. P., Townsend, S. R., Linde-Zwirble, W. T., Marshall, J. C., Bion, J., . . . Angus, D. C. (2010). The Surviving Sepsis Campaign: Results of an international guideline-based performance improvement program targeting severe sepsis. *Intensive Care Medicine*, *36*, 222-231. doi:10.100/s00134-0009-1738-3
- Li, Z., Xi, X., Luo, X., Li, J., & Li, J. (2013). Implementing Surviving Sepsis Campaign bundles in China: A prospective cohort study. *Chinese Medical Journal*, *126*, 1819-1825.
- Michael, M., Schaffer, S. D., Egan, P. L., Little, B. B., & Pritchard, P. S. (2013). Improving wait times and patient satisfaction in primary care. *Journal for Healthcare Quality*, *35*(2), 50-60. doi:10.1111/jhq.12004
- Mikkelsen, M. E., Gaieski, D. F., Goyal, M., Miltiades, A. N., Munson, J. C., Pines, J. M., . . . Christie, J. D. (2010). Factors associated with nonadherence to early goal-directed therapy in the ED. *Chest*, *138*, 551-558. doi:10.1378/chest.09-2210
- Mori, C. (2014). A-voiding catastrophe: Implementing a nurse-driven protocol. *MEDSURG Nursing*, *23*, 15-28.
- Na, S., Kuan, W. S., Mahadevan, M., Li, C., Shrikhande, P., Sumit, R., . . . Nguyen, B. (2012). Implementation of early goal-directed therapy and the Surviving Sepsis Campaign resuscitation bundle in Asia. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, *24*, 452-462.
- Nguyen, H. B., Corbett, S. W., Steele, R., Banta, J., Clark, R., Hayes, S., . . . Wittlake, W. A. (2007). Implementation of a bundle of quality indicator or the early management of severe sepsis and septic shock is associated with decreased mortality. *Critical Care Medicine*, *35*, 1105-1112.
- O'Neill, R., Morales, J., & Jule, M. (2012). Early goal-directed therapy (EGDT) for severe sepsis/septic shock: Which components of treatment are more difficult to implement in a community-based emergency department? *Journal of Emergency Medicine*, *42*, 503-510.

- Perry, J., Bell, F., Shaw, T., Fitzpatrick, B., & Sampson, E. L. (2014). The use of PDSA methodology to evaluate and optimise an inner city memory clinic: A quality improvement project. *BMC Geriatrics, 14*(4), 1-5. doi:10.1186/1471-2318-14-4
- Robbins, C. M., Stillwell, T., Johnson, D., Wilson, S., & Fitzgerald, L. (2013). Integrating patient safety and clinical pharmacy services into the care of a high-risk, ambulatory population: A collaborative approach. *Journal of Patient Safety, 9*, 110-117. doi:10.1097/PTS.0b013e318281b879
- Robson, W., Beavis, S., & Spittle, N. (2007). An audit of ward nurses' knowledge of sepsis. *Nursing in Critical Care, 12*, 86-92.
- Schorr, C., Zanotti, S., & Dellinger, R. (2013). Severe sepsis and septic shock. *Virulence, 5*, 190-200. doi:10.4161/viru.27409
- Shorr, A. F., Micek, S. T., Jackson, W. L., & Kollef, M. H. (2007). Economic implications of an evidence-based sepsis protocol: Can we improve outcomes and lower costs? *Critical Care Medicine, 35*, 1257-121261. doi:10.1097/01.CCM.0000261886.65063.CC
- Stamataki, P., Papazafiropoulou, A., Kalaitzi, S., Sarafis, P., Kagialari, M., Adamou, E., . . . Giamarellou, E. (2013). Knowledge regarding assessment of sepsis among Greek nurses. *Journal of Infection Prevention, 13*(2), 58-63. doi:10.1177/1757177413513816
- Stearns-Kurosawa, D., Osuchowski, M. F., Valentine, C., Kurosawa, S., & Remick, D. (2011). The pathogenesis of sepsis. *Annual Review of Pathology: Mechanisms of Disease, 6*, 19-48. doi:10.1146/annurev-pathol-0111110-130327
- Tromp, M., Tjan, D. H. T., Zanten, A. R. H., Gielen-Wijffels, S. E. M., Goekoop, G. J. D., Boogaard, M., . . . Pickkers, P. (2011). The effects of implementation of the surviving sepsis campaign in the Netherlands. *Netherland Journal of Medicine, 69*, 292-298.
- Wang, Z., Xiong, Y., Schorr, C., & Dellinger, R. P. (2013). Impact of sepsis bundle strategy on outcomes of patients suffering from severe sepsis and septic shock in China. *Journal of Emergency Medicine, 44*, 735-742. doi:10.1016/j.jemermed.2012.07.084
- Yealy, D. M., Kellum, J. A., Huang, D. T., Barnato, A. E., Weissfeld, L. A., & Pike, F. (2014). A randomized trial of protocol-based care for early septic shock. *The New England Journal of Medicine, 370*, 1683-1693. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1401602
- Ziglam, H. M., Morales, D., Webb, K., & Nathwani, D. (2006). Knowledge about sepsis among training-grade doctors. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy, 57*, 963-965. doi:10.1093/jack/dk1042

APPENDIX A

PERMISSION TO UTILIZE FRAMEWORK

Cal State Fullerton Mail - Model for Improvement - PDSA

3/29/14 8:35 PM

Yu-Ching Lee <kalee@csu.fullerton.edu>

Model for improvement - PDSA

2 messages

Yu-Ching Lee <kalee@csu.fullerton.edu>

Fri, Feb 21, 2014 at 5:17 PM

To: jlangley@apiweb.org

Mr. Langley:

My name is Karen Lee, I am currently pursuing a doctoral of degree in nursing at California State Fullerton. The reason that I am contacting you is to ask for permission to use the PDSA model for my doctoral project. My project aims to improve the sepsis outcome and I believe the PDS model will provide guideline for my project to achieve the desired outcome.

Sincerely,

Karen Lee, FNP-C
 CSU DNP Program 2013-2015

Jerry Langley <jlangley@apiweb.org>

Fri, Feb 21, 2014 at 8:58 PM

Reply-To: jlangley@apiweb.org

To: Yu-Ching Lee <kalee@csu.fullerton.edu>

Karen Lee,

As long as you reference the source, we are happy for people to use the methods (including the PDSA) described in our book, *The Improvement Guide*, Jossey-Bass Second Edition, 2009.

Jerry

From: Yu-Ching Lee [mailto:kalee@csu.fullerton.edu]
Sent: Friday, February 21, 2014 5:17 PM**To:** jlangley@apiweb.org**Subject:** Model for improvement - PDSA

[Quoted text hidden]

APPENDIX B**SEPSIS AUDIT TOOL****Medical Record Review Tool**

1. Personal Biographical Data.
 - a. Gender: M, F
 - b. Age _____
 - c. Ethnicity White/Caucasian, Black,
 Asian/Pacific Islander, Hispanic,

2. Length of Stay: CC LOS _____, Non-CC LOS _____, Total LOS _____

3. Level of Care upon sepsis identification: Critical Care,
Emergency, Telemetry, Med/Surg, Other _____

	ICD 9	3-Hour Bundles				6-Hour Bundles		Disposition
		Blood culture prior to administration of antibiotic	Administration of broad spectrum antibiotic	Lactic acid level	30 ml/kg for hypotension or lactic acid \geq 36 mg/dL	Vasopressors for hypotension unresponsive to fluid resuscitation to keep MAP \geq 65	CVP monitoring	Expired, home, home health, LTAC, transfer, SNF, other _____
Chart #1		Yes___ No___ Comments:	Yes___ No___ Comments:	Yes___ No___ Comments:	Yes___ No___ Comments:	Yes___ No___ Comments:	Yes___ No___ Comments:	<input type="checkbox"/> Expired, <input type="checkbox"/> home, <input type="checkbox"/> home health, <input type="checkbox"/> LTAC <input type="checkbox"/> transfer, <input type="checkbox"/> SNF, <input type="checkbox"/> other
Chart #2		Yes___ No___ Comments:	Yes___ No___ Comments:	Yes___ No___ Comments:	Yes___ No___ Comments:	Yes___ No___ Comments:	Yes___ No___ Comments:	<input type="checkbox"/> Expired, <input type="checkbox"/> home, <input type="checkbox"/> home health, <input type="checkbox"/> transfer, <input type="checkbox"/> SNF, <input type="checkbox"/> other
Summary Percentage		_____ %	_____ %	_____ %	_____ %	_____ %	_____ %	_____ %

APPENDIX C
NURSE SURVEY

Consent

Implementation of a sepsis protocol

To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in a research project conducted by Dr. Ayman Tailakh, assistant professor of Nursing at California State University Los Angeles and Yu-Ching Karen Lee, a graduate student at California State University, Los Angeles. Your participation in this study is voluntary. The purpose of this study is to find if nurse's knowledge, attitudes and behaviors toward sepsis have an impact on patient outcome. We hope that our research will lead to a better understanding to improve sepsis management.

Please answer each question to the best of your knowledge and accordance to your current practice.

There are minimal risks associated with participation in this study. Reports resulting from this study will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this study will remain confidential and be given out only with your permission or as required by law. If you give us permission by signing this consent form, we will protect your confidentiality. This consent form and the questionnaire will be kept in separately locked drawer in principal investigator's office in the school of nursing on the California State University, Los Angeles campus for a minimum of three years following completion of study before destruction. Your participation in this study is voluntary.

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call Dr. Ayman Tailakh at 323-343-4196 or write him at ayman.tailakh@calstatela.edu or Yu-Ching Karen Lee at xxx-xxx-xxxx at xxxxx@csu.fullerton.edu.

By signing this consent form you indicate that you have read the form and agree voluntarily to participate in the study. If you choose not to take part there will be no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled. If you agree to take part, you are free to withdraw from it at any time. Likewise, no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled will occur.

I agree to participate in Implementation of a sepsis protocol, as set out above.

Signature

Date

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN REVIEWED BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH. ADDITIONAL CONCERNS AND COMPLAINTS, OR QUESTIONS REGARDING YOUR RIGHTS AS A RESEARCH PARTICIPANT, SHOULD BE DIRECTED TO THE ASSOCIATE VICE PRESIDENT FOR RESEARCH AND ACADEMIC PERSONNEL (Phone number: [323-343-3798](tel:323-343-3798)).

STUDY SURVEY

California State University, Los Angeles School of Nursing

IMPLEMENTATION OF A SEPSIS PROTOCOL: A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

Please **DO NOT** write your name on this form

- ❖ Please answer every question
- ❖ All answers you give will be completely **confidential**
- ❖ If you come to a question that you do not wish to answer, feel free to skip ahead to the next question
- ❖ If you do not know how to answer a question, please ask the researcher or the research assistant

**THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR YOUR
PARTICIPATION IN THIS IMPORTANT PROJECT!**

Demographic Data

I. DIRECTIONS: *The following are questions about you. Please fill in the blanks or check the answer that best describes you.*

1. What is your age? _____ years old
2. What is your gender?
1 Female 2 Male
3. What is your marital status?
1 Single 3 Divorced/Separated
2 Married 4 Widowed
4. What is the highest level of education you have completed?
1 Diploma 4 Graduate/Post Graduate
2 Associate degree
3 Bachelor's degree
5. Which one of the following best describes your employment status?
1 Employed full time 3 Per Diem
2 Employed part time
6. Which one of the following best describes the job title of your nursing position?
(Check only one.)
1 RN 2 LVN
7. In what year did you graduate from your Nursing Program? _ _ _ _
8. In what unit do you work: 1 Critical Care, 2 Emergency, 3 Telemetry,
4 Med/surg, 5 Other _____

II. **DIRECTIONS**: For question 1-8, check the box with the best answer

	True	False	I don't know
1. The active participation of nurses in medical care team's discussions about sepsis is essential	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Nurses should be continually updated with lectures/workshops/conferences/seminars about sepsis	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. The application of new data regarding the prevention and treatment of sepsis is used in the daily practice	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Patients in septic shock have hypotension despite intravascular volume restoration with fluids.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. When I notice that the patient fulfills the criteria of sepsis, I should inform my colleagues directly and precisely	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Signs such as vomiting, diarrhea, gastroparesis, ileum may be an early sign of organ dysfunction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. I consider that my patient has the septic syndrome, when the level of consciousness alters	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. The scoring assessing system for sepsis is used in daily practice in my working place	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

For question 9 and 10, check all applicable answers:

9. Which of the following is/are in the definition of systemic inflammatory response:

- Body temperature $>38^{\circ}\text{C}$ or Body temperature $<36^{\circ}\text{C}$
- Tachycardia
- Tachypnea
- $\text{WBC} > 12,000/\text{mm}^3$

10. Which of the following sign/s, increase/s the suspicion of a patient in sepsis:

- The fall in of mean arterial pressure $<65\text{mmHg}$
- Blood glucose $>120\text{ mg / dL}$ in non-diabetic patient
- Reduction of hourly urine excretion
- Increased Fe and serum ferritin
- Decrease in Oxygen saturation

APPENDIX D

TABLES OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Table 1

Significance and Epidemiology of Sepsis

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
Inpatient sepsis statistics (Hall et al., 2014)	N/A	N/A	N/A	<p>Hospitalization rate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2000—326,000/22.1 per 10,000 • 2008—727,000/37.7 per 10,000 • Under 65—9.5 per 10,000 • Over 65—122.2 per 10,000 • Over 65—271.2 per 10,000 <p>Complication rate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under 65—2x • Over 65—26% more likely <p>LOS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall 75% longer • Under 65—2x • Over 65—43% longer <p>Death and disposition: 17% of all inpatient death, half likely to DC home, 2x short-term acute, 3x long- term acute</p>	<p>Aging population with higher sepsis hospitalization</p> <p>Sepsis leads to longer stay and more complications</p>

Note. DC = discharge and LOS = length of stay.

Table 2

Framework: Model for Improvement and Plan-Do-Study-Act Cycle

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
SBHCs provide health promotion and disease prevention services. The goal is to improve access to care, increase preventative care, and lessen health disparity in disadvantaged population Quality improvement initiative to improve clinical services and delivery system in SBHC (Booker et al., 2011)	Quality improvement	14 high schools and 4 middle schools funded by New Mexico Department of Health during 2008-2009 school year 57 initial participants Inclusion: 16 hours per week of medical staff and program coordinator time	Model for improvement and PDSA tool to lead improvement. Use medical record data to track improvements Steps: 1. Presentation of the best practices model and related performance measure 2. Self-assessment of current performance by the SBHC staff 3. Review of a first set of medical records for the performance measures 4. Quality improvement methods training specific to the topic 5. Multiple additional record reviews to track improvements Impact measure: self-evaluations and medical record reviews at the SBHC site	Key areas of improvement: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pediatric overweight BMI documentation and key message (physical activity & nutrition habits) • Improved clinical practices through completion of student health questionnaire and documentation of early periodic screening diagnosis and treatment components • Behavior health by completion of student health questionnaire and documentation of risk assessed (signed, dated, and risk value) 	Provider perception of performance exceeded actual review of medical records. Model of improvement provided systematic process to monitor performance for improvement opportunity Limitations: lack of electronic data system, sampling bias, data error, and small sample data reviewed

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
Increase patient satisfaction by minimizing wait times utilizing PDSA improvement process (Michael et al., 2013)	Quality improvement pilot project Pretest and posttest design Convenience sampling 375 encounters in 1 week	Florida county health department adult primary care unit	Waiting room wait time: time elapsed between waiting room to time called to enter the exam room. Goal less than 20 minutes Exam room wait time: time elapsed from entering the exam room to time seen by a provider. Goal less than 10 minutes Patient satisfaction: 1. Satisfaction with waiting room wait time 2. Satisfaction with exam room wait time 3. Likelihood of referral to others	Postimplementation waiting room wait time 5.33 minutes shorter. Postimplementation exam room wait time 1.81 minute shorter Other factors: turnaround time for return phone calls and time waiting for laboratory test and results	PDSA cycle was effective in reducing wait time. A second cycle is necessary to focus on clinical process
To reduce patient wait time using PDSA tool (Perry et al., 2014)	Quality improvement program	Haringey Memory Service in London Convenience sampling—79 in 2011 and 79 in 2012 Exclusion: patient did not attend first appointment or has pending appointment; already had a	Wait time—referral to assessment and referral to diagnosis	First, PDSA decreased referral to assessment from 35.7 to 29.7 weeks Second, PDSA decreased referral to assessment from 29.7 to 9.3 weeks Referral to initial assessment appointment increased from 9.3 to 10.9 weeks possibly due to increased number of patient referrals to the clinic. Referral to diagnosis decreased from 15.11 to 14.2 weeks	PDSA is a continuous quality improvement process that has demonstrated its effectiveness. It is applicable to other situation to for quality improvement purpose

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
		diagnosis or had diagnoses pending		Third, PDSA decreased referral to diagnosis and referral to treatment time	
				Brain scan time decreased	
To facilitate integration of pharmacy practices to enhance patient safety utilizing model for improvement (Robbins et al., 2013)	Quality improvement project	Lincoln Community Health Center in Durham, North Carolina 715 specialists and 1,725 patients from 7/2008- 12/2009	Medication reconciliation completion—patients with written documentation of current medications with dosage including prescription medications, over-the-counter medications, and herbal supplements Obesity—BMI documentation within 12 months and obesity discussion at follow-up Patient safety relating to adverse drug event—percentage of adverse drug events receiving clinical pharmacy services	54 PDSA cycles Medication reconciliation from 0%-100%, BMI documentation from 75%-100%, increased patient safety, and less adverse drug events from more prescriptions processed by trained specialists	PDSA cycle helped to integrate clinical pharmacy services and improved all targeted outcomes

Note. BMI = body mass index, PDSA = plan do study act, and SBHC = school-based health center.

Table 3

Guidelines for Sepsis Treatment

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
Guideline for sepsis treatment (Dellinger et al., 2013)	Consensus of committee of 68 international experts representing 30 international organizations Use of Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation system to guide assessment of quality evidence	N/A		Protocolized approach via EGDT	
Implementation of Protocol Watch to increase SSC measures (Giuliano et al., 2011)	Pilot study Preintervention and postintervention comparison	Critical care units at St. Vincent's Medical Center in Bridgeport, Connecticut, and Legacy Healthcare Good Samaritan Hospital in Portland, Oregon	Comparison of study variables before and after intervention	Increased compliance in resuscitation bundle 57.6% to 68.2% Decreased time to antibiotic administration 181.9 minutes to 112.4 minutes	Compliance potentially improves sepsis outcome by reducing morbidity and mortality

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
Implementation of severe sepsis bundle in an emergency room (Nguyen et al., 2007)	Prospective observational cohort 3 months each phase: baseline, education, operational, and 5 quality improvement phases	Academic tertiary care facility 330 patients with severe sepsis and/or septic shock in ER	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CVP/SvcO2 monitoring within 2 hours 2. Broad-spectrum antibiotic within 4 hours 3. Completed EGDT at 6 hours 4. Corticosteroid for patient on vasopressor or if adrenal insufficiency is suspected 5. Monitoring of lactate clearance 	<p>Mortality reduction when: received antibiotic within 4 hours ↓ OR 0.38, received EGDT at 6 hours ↓ OR 0.55, lactate clearance ↓ OR 0.49, and bundle completion ↓ OR 0.4</p> <p>Mortality for bundle completion OR 0.36—significant quality indicator</p> <p>Mortality for EGDT completion 25.8%, mortality for EGDT incomplete 38.8%</p>	Severe sepsis bundle can be implemented to standard care among physicians and nurses improve outcome
Summary of 2013 SSC guidelines and highlights of hospital-based performance improvement programs (Schorr et al., 2013)	N/A	N/A	N/A		

Note. CVP = central venous pressure, EGDT = early goal-directed therapy, SSC = Surviving Sepsis Campaign, and SvcO2 = superior vena cava oxygen saturation.

Table 4

Barriers to Early Goal-Directed Therapy

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
Identification of barriers to underutilization of EGDT in facility with formalized protocol (Mikkelsen et al., 2010)	Observational study	University of Pennsylvania ED 2005-2007 340 EGDT eligible, 18-101 years old—54% septic shock, 46% occult shock Inclusion: lactate done in ED or EMR documentation of sepsis, severe sepsis, septic shock or EGDT Exclusion: lactate not done in ED, patient refused CVC	Case report form—patient, physician, and organizational data extracted from EMR EGDT initiation—measurement of ScvO ₂ via CVC EGDT completion—CVP ≥ 8 mmHg, MAP ≥ 65 mmHg, and ScvO ₂ $\geq 70\%$	Severe sepsis protocol institute in 2004 for EGDT when lactate > 4 or SBP < 90 after 1,500 ml fluid resuscitation EGDT not initiated in 42%; EGDT incompleteness 43% EGDT patient received more intravenous fluids, vasoactive agents, and CVC Higher mortality in EGDT initiated 33% (30%) and incomplete 36% (30%) Patient factor: female gender, younger age, lower severity, higher MAP, lower lactate, lower APACHE II, absence of coagulation dysfunction, and cause of sepsis due to preexisting CVC Physician factor: female gender and greater years of practice less likely to comply with EGDT and use sepsis service	Limitations: single center and observational study Barriers to EGDT—patient, physician, and organizational factors Efforts should be concentrated on the factors identified to improve EGDT compliance

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
				<p>Organizational factor: utilization of serum lactate for EGDT eligibility instead of hemodynamic criteria, admission to nonmedical services, and failure to consult sepsis service</p> <p>Independent risk factors: female gender of patient, female gender of physician, utilization of lactate criterion, and failure to consult sepsis service</p>	
<p>Identification of specific elements of barrier to EGDT (O'Neill, Morales, & Jule, 2012)</p>	<p>Retrospective cohort analysis</p> <p>IV: lack of adequate time and staff, insertion of CVC, CVP monitor, physical ED space, communication with medical specialties, and appropriate patient ID, CC responsibility for sepsis treatment</p> <p>DV: EGDT</p>	<p>410-bed Michigan community hospital with 35-bed ED</p> <p>85 patients</p> <p>Inclusion: ≥ 18 years old with severe sepsis/septic shock by SSC guideline (79 patients)</p> <p>Exclusion: < 18 years old, pregnancy, trauma, burns, ACS, CVA, drug overdose, DNR, CVC contraindication, need for STAT surgery (13 patients)</p>	<p>Chart review then data entry into central database by principal investigator—standardized abstraction form and table of process measure</p> <p>Measurement of adherence to specific elements of protocol: fluid resuscitation, ABX within 1 hour, CVC, CVP, arterial line placement, vasopressor administration, ScvO₂ measurement, and standardized order set</p> <p>Survey</p>	<p>79/85 (93%) with correct diagnosis, vasopressin 50/63 (79%), ABX within 1 hour 66/85 (78%), order set used 59/85 (69%), fluid resuscitation 58/85 (68%), CVC 55/85 (65%), arterial line 36/85 (42%), CVP 23/85 (27%), and ScvO₂ 13/85 (15%)</p> <p>33% mortality rate and 57/85 (57%) survival. Patients with 1 hour diagnosis and fluid resuscitation have increased survival rate</p>	<p>Need for protocol champion and education program</p> <p>Barriers: physician too busy for CVC insertion, nurse unfamiliar with CVP and arterial line setup, and system failure</p> <p>Limitations: small sample, single site trial, selection bias, missed patient identification, and data error due to nonconcurrent review</p>

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
Compare the mortality of patients with (group 2) and without (group 1) the implementation of sepsis bundles in the ED	Prospect study. Before-and-after study design	195 cases. Group 1—55/78 (70.8%) severe sepsis and 23/78 (29.5%) septic shock. Group 2—81/117 (69.2%) severe sepsis and 36/117 (30.8%) septic shock	Intervention—SSC guideline given to ED MD. Protocol poster, daily patient screen, and compliance survey to identify failure to protocol compliance	Low baseline SSC compliance: (a) process of prescription dispensing, (b) lack of prioritization and adherence to med list, (c) MD unaware of ABX timeline, and (d) skin test prior to cephalosporin administration	Decreased mortality after implementing sepsis protocol and quality improvement bundles in the ED
	IV: SSC protocol and ICU admission DV: in-hospital sepsis mortality	Baseline—6/08-12/08 Intervention—1/09-12/09	Standardized data collection with SSC database case report forms	MD survey for noncompliance: 25.6% unsure, 16.4% forgot, 30.8% think no need, 5.8% did not know, 3.8% patient condition, and 17.6% MD or patient refusal	Barriers: knowledge, attitude, and behavioral barriers Limitations: single site study, small sample size, and low compliance
Identify barriers to EGDT (Wang et al., 2013)		A medical university-affiliated hospital in China with 1,200 beds and 15 ICU beds. ED with 500-600 visits per day Inclusion: severe sepsis or septic shock upon admission to the ED		Decreased mortality after SSC implementation Higher patient mortality in ED and not in ICU. Increased LOS and mortality with > 6-hour delay in ICU transfer. 20% admission rate with remainder treatment in ED due to bed availability	

Note. ABX = antibiotics, ACS = acute coronary syndrome, APACHE II = acute physiology and chronic health evaluation, CC = critical care, CVA = cerebral vascular accident, CVC = central venous catheter, CVP = central venous pressure, DV = dependent variables, ED = emergency department, EGDT = early goal-directed therapy, EMR = electronic medical record, ICU = intensive care unit, ID = identification, IV = independent variables, LOS = length of stay, MAP = mean arterial pressure, MD = medical doctor, SBP = systemic blood pressure, SvcO2 = serum central venous oxygen saturation, SSC = Surviving Sepsis Campaign, and STAT = now.

Table 5

Surviving Sepsis Campaign Bundle Compliance and Patient Outcomes

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
Reduction in mortality with sepsis patients when SSC bundle implementation (Cardoso et al., 2010)	Prospective cohort design	Multicenter in Portuguese 12/2004-11/2005 17 ICU, 778 patients Inclusion: > 18 years with severe sepsis upon ICU admission	Time zero—hospital arrival time	Compliance: Overall 12%, lactate 62%, fluid 69%, blood culture 48%, antibiotics 52%, vasopressors 78%, CVP 56%, ScvO ₂ 17% Full compliance associated with decrease in 28-day mortality severe sepsis OR 0.44 with 6 to treat, septic shock OR 0.49 34% mortality versus 25% mortality with bundle completion	Completion of core bundle = better outcome Better outcome with full bundle implementation compared to partial compliance
Examine outcome after implementing SSC (Castellanos- Ortega et al., 2010)	Quasi- experimental	3 med/surg ICU 384 patients in educational intervention group, 96 historical group 6/2005-8/2005	In-hospital mortality, ICU mortality, hospital LOS, ICU LOS and bundle compliance	Mortality—historical 57.3% versus intervention 37.5% Overall LOS 41-36.2 days, ICU LOS 11 to 8.4 days	Improvement in mortality rate and decrease in ICU LOS

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
Examining sepsis patient outcome by implementing SSC bundle (Levy et al., 2010)	Prospective	Voluntary participation. Recruitment through professional critical care congress, SSC, and IHI websites 15,022 subjects in 165 sites between 1/2005-3/2008 Exclusion: < 20 subjects	Compliance—evidence that all bundle elements were achieved within indicated timeframe Hospital mortality, LOS, and ICU LOS	Bundle targets—10.9% to 31.3% (6-hour bundle), 18.4 to 36.1% (24-hour bundle) Mortality—37% to 30.8%; 91% decrease per quarter Elements associated with lower mortality: broad-spectrum antibiotic—OR 0.86, blood culture—OR 0.76, glucose control—OR 0.67	SSC increased compliance that lead to better patient outcomes Early identification of infection and initiation of antibiotic is essential Limitations: voluntary data, generalizability, and not RCT
Comparison of sepsis care model, outcomes, mortality, and LOS in United States and Europe (Levy et al., 2012)	Prospective cohort study IV: admission criteria and protocol difference in United States and Europe DV: outcome, mortality, and LOS	107 sites with 18,766 patients in United States, 79 sites with 6,609 patients in Europe, total of 25,375 patients Patients with severe sepsis or septic shock according to SSC data Inclusion—each site with at least 20 patients and at least 3 months of enrollment	SSC database Table 1. Descriptive statistics by region Table 2. Compliance with sepsis care measures	United States > Europe ICU admission from ER Europe—longer general ward stay prior to ICU, multiple organ failure, more nosocomial infection, vent, longer LOS, and higher mortality United States—single organ failure and higher resuscitation bundle compliance	Origin of patients prior to ICU admission is the major difference Patients with sepsis in Europe are more ill Limitations: not randomized study due to voluntary SSC database entry in United States and Europe, results not representative of region, and true mortality rate not captured due to only ICU patients are in the database excluding patients not in ICU

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
Examining SSC bundle compliance and patient outcome (Li et al., 2013)	Prospective observational cohort design	Multicenter ICU, 9/2007- 10/2008 219 patients/ 3,406 screened Exclusion: < 18 years, pregnancy, GCS < 5, require immediate surgery, terminal condition, other complications	Data collection— practitioner survey and case report form Outcome—compliance and mortality	86% physicians familiar with SSC Overall 28-day mortality 33%; overall LOS 14, ICU LOS 10 Complications: hypotension, hyperlactatemia, respiratory failure, renal failure, hyperbilirubinemia, thrombocytopenia, coagulopathy, and organ failure Overall compliance 42.2%; 5-7 protocol—OR 0.33	Implementation of 6-hour bundle is associated with decrease in 28-day mortality rate
Examination of the impact of implementation of sepsis bundle (Na et al., 2012)	Prospective cohort design	8 urban hospitals from 5 countries in Asia 7/1/2008-12/31/2008 556 patients Inclusion: adults > 18 years with severe sepsis or septic shock	Education done in 2008— definition and treatment Team model— championed by intensivists with bundles completed in ICU Nonteam model—led of ER physicians with bundles completed in ER as standard of care	Overall mortality 29.9%. Bundle completion reduced mortality OR 0.67 Compliance 13.3%, 26.9%, 37.5%, 45.9%, 48.8%, and 54.5% with each quarter, team model compliance 37.5% to 88.2%, and nonteam model 5.2% to 39.5%	

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements and Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, and Notes
Sepsis protocol improve survival and result in cost saving (Shorr et al., 2007)	Retrospective analysis of before-after study	120 patients with sepsis Tertiary academic centers in United States	Protocol based on SSC	28-day mortality 48.3% to 30% Average per patient cost saving \$6,000, \$573,000 between groups ICU utilization decreased by 35%, ward utilization 30% Hospital LOS decreased by 5 days from 13 to 8 days, > 2 weeks LOS 36.7% preintervention versus 13% postintervention, and 20% > 20 days versus 8.3% postintervention	Better outcome with SSC implementation including survival, LOS, and cost
Comparison of the Netherlands and international bundle compliance and mortality after implementation of SSC (Tromp et al., 2011)	Observational design	1,172 patients in the Netherlands, 15,022 patients from 165 sites internationally 12/2005-6/2009 Inclusion: > 18 years	Resuscitation bundle elements	Bundle compliance—8-48%. Mortality—52%-35%	Bundle compliance increased and mortality decreased after implementation of SSC

Note. CVP = central venous pressure, DV = dependent variables, ER = emergency room, GCS = Glasgow Coma Scale, ICU = intensive care unit, ID = independent variables, LOS = length of stay, OR = odds ratio, RCT = randomized controlled trial, Scvo2 = superior vena cava oxygen saturation, and SSC = Surviving Sepsis Campaign.

